

Chemical constituents of *Citrus sinensis* juice variety Pineapple

Geeta R. Arora, Lalita Yadav and Suraj B. Kalidhar*

Department of Chemistry and Physics, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar-125 004, Haryana, India

E-mail : sbkalidhar@gmail.com

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Abstract : Phytochemical study of *Citrus sinensis* juice var. Pineapple has resulted in the isolation of five compounds namely nonacosan-15-one, β -sitosterol, epi- α -amyrin, methyl nonacosanoate and octacosanoic acid. β -Sitosterol is a known compound from this plant. The other four compounds namely nonacosan-15-one, epi- α -amyrin, methyl nonacosanoate and octacosanoic acid are being reported for the first time from the juice of this plant. Biochemical parameters in the juice were found to be comparable with those of other *C. sinensis* varieties.

Keywords : *Citrus sinensis*, Pineapple, Rutaceae, nonacosan-15-one, β -sitosterol, epi- α -amyrin, methyl nonacosanoate, octacosanoic acid, biochemical parameters.

Introduction

Citrus sinensis (L.) Osbeck (syn, *C. aurantium* L. var. *sinensis*) belongs to family Rutaceae¹ and commonly known as sweet orange or mosambi. *C. sinensis* var. Pineapple belongs to round oranges cultivated in Punjab, Haryana and Rajasthan². Due to its similarity of its flavour to that of pineapple, it was named as Pineapple. Tree moderately vigorous, medium large, thornless, productive and sensitive to frost. Fruits are medium sized, subglobose. Rind is thin, tight, smooth, bright and glossy. Pulp is orange yellow, abundant, melting, flavour rich, acidity and sweetness well blended³. The plant possesses a very high medicinal value. Leaves of the plant are used as remedies for internal ailments and fractures as well as other sickness. Juice of the fruit together with coconut oil or castor oil is used as purgative⁴. The ripe fruit is strengthening, cardiotoxic, laxative, anthelmintic, removes fatigue. The flower is stimulant, its smell relieves cold, its juice is tonic, diuretic, useful in piles and in enlargement of spleen. The rind is anthelmintic, good in vomiting and in skin diseases, its juice stops bilious diarrhoea⁵ and act as expectorant in bronchitis, asthma and emphysema⁶.

The plant is a rich source of flavonoids. The PMFs (polymethoxylated flavones) in *Citrus* have been shown to exhibit anticancer effects against human cancer cell

lines as well as anti-inflammatory and cardiotoxic actions⁷. Alcoholic extract of *C. sinensis* shows the highest anti-oxidant activity⁸.

In view of scanty data available on the chemical components of Pineapple juice, we have undertaken the present investigation. Five compounds have been isolated and characterized. Biochemical parameters have also been determined.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on Ganson Electrical Melting Point Apparatus. ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) on Bruker AC-400F MHz NMR spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard. IR spectra were obtained on Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were recorded on VG-70S 11-250J GC-MS-DS Mass spectrometer.

C. sinensis var. Pineapple fruits (15 kg) were collected from Department of Horticulture, CCS HAU, Hisar. Fruits were squeezed to get juice. The juice was divided into two parts. One part was used for determining biochemical parameters. Another part of the juice was washed with ethyl acetate four times. The extract so obtained was concentrated on water bath under reduced pressure to obtain viscous mass. The viscous mass thus obtained was

mixed with silica gel (60–120 mesh), dried on water bath and subjected to column chromatography over silica gel (60–120 mesh) with solvents of increasing polarity and five compounds were isolated.

Another part of the juice was used for determining biochemical parameters : total sugars, tannins, titrable acidity, TSS ascorbic acid content in the juice of Pineapple as per standard methods.

Nonacosan-15-one (1) was obtained on elution with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 19) as colourless waxy solid and crystallized from methanol, 30 mg, m.p. 82 °C (lit.⁹ m.p. 80.5–81 °C).

β-Sitosterol (2) was obtained on elution with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 9) and it crystallized out from benzene as white solid, 40 mg, m.p. 135 °C (lit.¹⁰ m.p. 136–137 °C).

Epi-α-amyrin (3) was obtained on elution with ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 3). It crystallized out from methanol, 30 mg, m.p. 112 °C (lit.¹¹ m.p. 110–111 °C).

Methyl nonacosanoate (4) was obtained on elution with ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 9). It crystallized out from methanol, 18 mg, m.p. 70 °C (lit.¹² m.p. 68.8 °C).

Octacosanoic acid (5) was obtained on elution with ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 3). It crystallized out from the methanol, 12 mg, m.p. 88 °C (lit.¹³ m.p. 89.5–90.5 °C).

The juice of *C. sinensis* var. Pineapple contained total sugar (17.50 g/100 ml)^{14,15}, tannins (44.50 mg/100 ml)^{16,17}, ascorbic acid (55.23 mg/100 ml)^{18,19}, TSS (9.20%)^{3,17} and titrable acidity (3.22 g/100 ml)^{18,20}.

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